

Control Modelling of Cognitive Response States and Predicting with Emoticons on Optical Stimulus for Optimized Affect State.

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Abstract

A dynamic control model is based on a mathematical representation of the dynamics that exist between the inputs and the outputs of an active system. In terms of the physical representation of physiological responses such as skin conductance response, pupil dilation, and emotion recognition, this can be represented in the form of physiological control systems where the reactions of a natural phenomenon are represented as the mechanical interaction between a person and the object of interest, for this case the optical stimulus as a business webpage. This paper aims to highlight more on the representation of the cognitive response of users as emoticons conveyed to optical stimulus based on dynamic control optimization of a minimization problem. The input parameter includes eye movements with recorded pupil dilation and mouse clicks that correlate to gaze points or fixation location. The model is represented as a window-based dynamic control with a set module for each interphase that predicts the users' cognitive response to the optical visual display as emotive emoticons for precognitive analysis. The output shows users expressed more neutral responses than either stressed or relaxed mood to the product they viewed online.

Keywords : *Dynamic control optimization, Emotive emoticons, Cognitive response, Precognitive analysis, Optical stimulus, Business webpage*

1 Introduction

The use of dynamic control models is normally represented as a form differential equation, the loop or feedback system's controller monitors the output of the plant to adjust the main actuators to produce a specified response. Physical systems as experimental data

can be developed as a dynamic system mode (Figure 2), where the inputs represent references as parameters X (eye movement activities) and the controller is a black box that produces the physical representation of the mechanism of the system through actuators and sensors (eye tracking sensors) the output is a well-predicted visual response to the optical stimuli.

The output system is a representation of the cognitive response of users to optical stimulus, this is obtained from data generated from the pre-designed experiment. The business webpage is a more suitable base for an optical stimulus that can induce a cognitive response from people who view products without subjective views. There is also a peculiar view in the business sector that emotions from users belong to liberal intuition that traditional-progressive contrast. Cognitive emotional responses are linked to well-being and non-cognitive factors. The science behind cognitive factors is that emotions are an important factor in the processes and emoticons are emblems that can instantly depict what a person feels. Emotive emoticons are an important factor in cognitive processes according to recent studies [10, 16, 6, 15, 8, 2, 11, 7].

Emotive emoticons can represent important rules as a text-based expression to illustrate attention, memory, and decisions of a particular person and also actions based on motivations. Sometimes we do not know how to represent the experience of the basic emotions of users during an online survey and also subjective measures might not be enough, because users don't normally know what they feel, for instance, anger, sadness, and happiness might an obvious response, but what can we say about curiosity, boredom, and interest? Which are detected from physiological readings of the person. Some research [17, 5, 13, 21, 20, 14, 3, 12, 18, 19] concluded that there is no real consensus and emotions are also dependent on the language used to name them. That is one might be feeling happy, and yet the happiness is connected to melancholy. Text-based expressions such as emotive emoticons can serve as a unique icon [9, 4, 1], to identify a specific response if mapped by a controlled inference engine and represented in a physical mode. These emoticons can be represented as an important part of the cognitive processes of a person through an optimization of the dynamic control process based on minimization problems like the one given in Equation 2.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimise}_P \|y_t - y_n\|_n \\ & \text{subject to } 0 = f\left(\frac{dx}{dt}, x, y, p\right) \\ & 0 \leq g\left(\frac{dx}{dt}, x, y, p\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where x and y are input and output parameters of the functions f and g that represent the control models' soft parameters in the basic control loop of Figure 2.

2 Method

The initial stage of the project was to collect data from participants by designing an experimental study where sixty (60) participants were involved sitting in front of a PC with an embedded webcam (Figure 3). The participant's eyes were calibrated to the monitor's

screen which set the ground for perfect eye movement recordings. The second stage was to design a window-based dynamic control system that serves as the inference engine to accept input.

Algorithm 1 Subject's eye detection and tracking

Require: Ready subject's iris 0

Ensure: (item eye position, Current location

Set pupil localisation

Trace iris position

$iris \leftarrow lens$

while latency $\neq 0$ **do**

if eyes are closed, wait **then**

 Record eye current location

$latency \leftarrow \frac{latency}{2}$ ▷ Response detected

else if goto line3 **then**

$Latency \leftarrow Latency - 1$

end if

if the eye is open and no iris detected **then**

 Update current location

$latency \leftarrow \frac{latency}{2}$ ▷ Response detected

else if goto line 3 **then**

for each user **do**

 Update pupil size

 Update Current location

End For

end if

end while

data and perform standard analysis from a separate PC. Both PCs were used for the experimental wireless inclined for easy export and visualization of data. The eye tracking algorithm (Algorithm 2) is used to record eye movement activities, mouse and keyboard press with a processing speed as fast as 200MHz per second, this is recorded as fast as in milliseconds and can a single user data to ten minutes equivalent to two thousand instances for a single user. The sixty participants' data produces instances close to twenty thousand and serves as the input data model to the control systems. The next algorithm (Algorithm 2) is used to predict the user gaze point based on user activities and users' emotions are expressed as emotive emoticons based simulated sample set.

2.1 Task

The participants were simply asked to interact with three business webpages and respond to the product they liked or admired. The behaviour and search mode are simply restricted to a simple search on a single page to get the eye movement in synchronous with mouse activities.

The task is set to induce happiness as well as relaxation for a simple webpage; other emotive responses from the participants could be due to the complexity of a page that would cause either stress or confusion. For the

FIGURE 1 – Dynamic control system for cognitive response prediction to optical stimulus.

FIGURE 2 – The basic control system for dynamic models cognitive response prediction.

Algorithm 2 Emotion prediction on optical stimulus (webpages)

Require: Emoji Emblems, Object detector 0

Ensure: (Detected object

UpdateItem (item objects location, frame (j))

Trace iris position

$iris \leftarrow lens$

while $url(j) = 1 : N(urls) \neq 0$ **do**

if emoji set = emotion(1) **then**

 Initialise Algorithm 2 as an object detector

 Read in web url and run the detector (Algo 2)

 Read Emoji correlates from database ▷

Synchronised events

 Detect feature points using Algo 2

 Extract feature point descriptors as emoji sign

else if goto line 3 **then**

 Find the putative point matches

 Locate the object in the scene using step 8

 Detect another optimal response

end if

if $url(i) = N(url)$ **then**

 Update current location

$latency \leftarrow \frac{latency}{2}$ ▷ Response detected

else if goto line 6, goto 16 **then**

for each webpage **do**

 Set to current url

 Update object position

 Update frame

End For

end if

end while

FIGURE 3 – An example of participants sitting in front of a PC embedded with a webcam for eye calibration and movement on a business webpage.

project, the classes of emotion to represent emotive emoticons includes “Relaxed mood”, “Neutral mood”, “Stressed mood” and “Confused mood”. These moods are set as emotive emblems and mapped to the Cartesian coordinates of the webpages. The pupil response to the optical stimulus is a major attribute that is set and contributes greatly to the emotional response of the participants, it not only tells of changes in light intensity but also an underlying user response to a displayed stimulus. The generated data are easily recorded and collected as input for the dynamic system, the following section discusses the results and window outputs of the analysis.

3 Result

The dynamic control model begins with an index page where any website or address is entered, the address could be based on what the users interact with; for this case, the business webpages are saved in static format to run the analysis of the user interaction, other contributing parameters includes the fixation duration and coordinates of fixation points, other non-numeric attributes are the letter words from keyboard press and mouse click that correlates with the eye movement on the webpages. Figure 4 shows the index where one can enter the web address or URL of the optical stimulus which is a simple business page that the users visited. The model is set to inform analytics that can easily import a large number of datasets of user browsing habits both non-numerical and numerical attributes; these are saved within the archives in static form and called during analysis.

FIGURE 4 – Index page of the dynamic model for entry of URLs and other business webpages addresses.

Figure 5 shows a list of the static webpages saved for reanalysis, each user’s activity and eye movement are also saved for each page the users visited. The most useful approach to make sense of a user’s response on any business webpage is to generate a form of user-type data like the one generated from the experiment, this is also superficially similar to creating personas, and far less an intensive approach to comprehending the classes of emotional and behaviour that are primarily grounded in the fixation behaviour of the users. Also, the user type is useful in interpretations rather than predictions, but a combination of both can give more insight into the emotional and behavioural profiles of the users. The webpages are saved in PDF to capture every visual field and area of interest (AOI) from the optical stimulus based on the fact that different types of users place distinct emphasis on attention i.e. their visual scanning and make evaluations based on different priorities and sensitivities. The eye tracking measures help to locate the user activities and the saved samples are used to predict the moods of the user on the webpages.

Figure6 below shows a database of Emoticons that represent users’ moods, each emoji is characterized by four basic moods experienced by users on the product

they admired online for the case of confused and neutral mood is the most reactive mood and each mood can be classified based on a single run from the dynamic control model. Also, each mood is mapped to its corresponding coordinates and correlates to time duration that reflects significant pupil dilation and constriction during response spikes.

The emoticons are mapped to the visual optical field based on the predicted cognitive response of the user, for instance, if fixations are spatial on a particular area of point, the corresponding cognitive response is automatically interpreted as interest, and a mapped emoji is identified to such as case, depending on the duration, the mood is either expressed as relaxed of stress mood. Figure 7 shows a unified business webpage with predicted moods and neutral-faced emoji as the most predicted response on the pages. and it is also a dual-page business site with two different products with distinct backgrounds, the neutral face emoji is the most predicted cognitive response of the users to the product based on an aggregate of users’ responses. The stress mood is predicted less than the other user moods and can be interpreted that users are mostly neutral to what they look at online before purchasing the product

4 Conclusion

The paper aims to use a dynamic control model to optimise and predict the cognitive response of users to optical stimuli as webpages they interacted with, the input parameter includes eye movements with recorded pupil dilation and mouse clicks that correlate to gaze points or fixation location. The model is represented as a window-based dynamic control with a set module for each interphase that predicts the users’ cognitive response to the optical visual display as emotive emoticons for precognitive analysis. The output shows users expressed a more neutral response than either stress or relaxed mood to the product they viewed online. The form of analytical approach can be used both to quantify user experience data and also to predict and visualize user mood. The future perspective would be to compare the performance of the dynamic model optimization with deep learning algorithms to detect users’ moods based on facial expressions. This can serve as an integration of the physiological response of users to optical stimuli web correlates and this can be evaluated more precisely.

Acknowledgement

The author would like to thank Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria, for their sponsor of this paper.

FIGURE 5 – Window showing a list of saved web URLs with a static rendered format for analysis.

FIGURE 6 – The database of emoticons used to predict user moods.

FIGURE 7 – Emoji faces on dual paged business webpage.

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